

Comparative Study between Dynamic Hip Screws (DHS) and Plating Proximal Femoral Nailing (PFN) for Trochanteric Fracture of FemurSukomal Sarkar¹, Snehasish Datta², Sankar Deb Roy³, Ijack Debbarma⁴¹MS Orthopedic, Agartala Government Medical College and GB Hospital²MS Orthopedic, Agartala Government Medical College and GB Hospital³MS Orthopedic, Agartala Government Medical College and GB Hospital⁴MS Orthopedic, Agartala Government Medical College and GB Hospital

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Background: Dynamic Hip Screw (DHS) has been demonstrated to yield positive outcomes especially in cases of unstable intertrochanteric fracture. The DHS device, however, works less effectively in unstable fractures and has a comparatively greater incidence of internal fixation failure. Contrary, one of Proximal Femoral Nailing (PFN's) benefits is that it acts as a buttress to prevent the proximal fragment from translating laterally. The implant is more resilient to the binding force because of the intramedullary placement of the nail and lag screw interface.

Aim: To compare DHS and Plating PFN for Trochanteric fracture of Femur.

Method: For the comparative study of DHS and PFN groups data on intraoperative, early (within the first month following hip fracture surgery), and late (beyond the first month) difficulties was acquired and analysed. Their functional result was assessed using the Harris Hip Scores. The unpaired t-test and the Fisher exact test were used to compute and compare the groups.

Results: The Nonunion complication was found in 1 patient in both PFN and DHS group and implant failure was found among 3 patients of PFN and 4 patients of DHS group. Moreover, deep inflation was found in 1 patient of both groups. Intraoperative complications like improper insertion of compression screw were found in 3 patients, and varus angulation was found in 4 patients of DHS group. On the other hand, complications like failure to achieve closed reduction was found in 3 patients, and failure to put de-rotation screw was reported in 3 patients in PFN group. There were no statistically significant differences between the study groups when comparing the intra-operative findings ($p = 0.324$ for intra-operative complications).

Conclusion: PFN works better in unstable fractures while DHS yields functional outcomes that are compared in this study. Blood loss was observed to be lower in the PFN group, indicating a statistically significant correlation ($p < 0.005$). Furthermore, there are less negative results after PFN surgery. As a result, it is thought that the PFN technique of surgery is more precise and advantageous for patients to heal more quickly.

Keywords: Inter-trochanteric fracture, PFN, DHS.

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Background

Proximal Femoral Nail (PFN) and Dynamic Hip Screw (DHS) are two widely recognised surgical approaches for treating intertrochanteric (IT) hip fractures [1]. Although there has been a great deal of research on which is more effective in treating unstable fractures, there is less information available when it comes to stable fractures [2]. For the majority of intertrochanteric fractures, internal fixation is appropriate. The stability of the fracture determines the best type of fixation [3]. Fixation using an intramedullary or screw sliding plate device constitutes the cornerstone of treatment for intertrochanteric fractures. Therefore, the question of which treatment is better PFN or DHS remains open for debate [4].

Older adults and postmenopausal women are the most common populations to suffer from intratrochanteric (IT) hip fractures [5]. High-energy trauma is the most common cause of IT fractures in younger age groups. Given the increased frequency of Road Traffic Accidents (RTA) and the longer life spans, intratrochanteric fractures place a substantial strain on the worldwide healthcare system [6]. As a result, these fractures need to be fixed right away [7,8]. Although the DHS has been demonstrated to yield positive outcomes, complications are common, especially in cases of unstable intertrochanteric fracture [9]. The DHS device, however, works less effectively in unstable fractures and has a comparatively greater incidence of internal fixation failure [10]. On the other hand, PFN's benefits are

that it acts as a buttress to prevent the proximal fragment from translating laterally [11]. The implant is more resilient to the binding force because of the intramedullary placement of the nail and lag screw interface [12].

Aim: To compare DHS and Plating PFN for trochanteric fracture of femur.

Methods

It was a prospective, randomised comparative study, carried out on patients admitted to the Department of Orthopaedics. A total of 102 patients were considered for study (51 in DHS and PFN group). The following were the eligibility requirements for the patients who took part in the study:

- Patients who belonged to the age group of 50 years,

- According to the OTA categorisation, intertrochanteric fracture type 31-A1, A2, and A3.

Each group's clinical outcome was examined, and data on intraoperative, early (within the first month following hip fracture surgery), and late (beyond the first month) problems was collected.

Statistical Analysis: The two groups were compared for age, sex, fracture pattern, length of incision, time of operation, average blood loss, and intraoperative complications using t-test for independent samples. The groups were computed and compared using Fisher exact test and unpaired t-test. Here, $p < 0.05$ was deemed significant in all analyses. The statistical software SPSS 29.0 (SPSS Inc., Chicago, Ill.) was used for the analyses.

Results

Table 1: Comparing Study Group

Study group	Sex		Age (Mean)	Fracture pattern		
				A1	A2	A3
PFN	Male	21	64.1 years	9	12	26
	Female	30				
DHS	Male	24	65.2 Years	30	14	7
	Female	27				

Table 1 has provided information related to the gender, mean age and pattern of fracture in each group. According to table 1, there were 21 male and 30 female in PFN group and mean age of these patients was 64.1 years. The pattern of fracture was A1 in 9 patients, A2 among 12 patients and A3 was identified in 26 patients. On the other hand, there were 24 male and 27 female in DHS group and mean age of

these patients was 65.2 years. The pattern of fracture was A1 in 30 patients, A2 among 14 patients and A3 was found in 7 patients. In addition to this, as per the AO/OTA classification A1 fractures are straightforward, two-part fractures; A2 fractures have many fragments; and A3 fractures comprise reverse oblique and transverse fracture patterns.

Table 2: Comparing Complications

Complications	PFN	DHS
Superficial infections	1	3
Non-union	1	1
Implant failure	3	4
Deep infection	0	1

According to table 2, the complications like superficial infections were found in 1 patient of PFN and 3 patients of DHS group. The Nonunion complication was found in 1 patient of group PFN and DHS and implant failure was found among 3 patients of PFN and 4 patients of DHS group. Moreover, deep infection was found in 1 patient of each group.

Incision size averages for DHS and PFN groups were 6 cm and 3 cm, respectively. 20 patients in the DHS group and 34 patients in the PFN group had outstanding results. Additionally, 26 patients in the DHS group and 15 patients in the PFN group had good results. Moreover, 6 patients in DHS and 3 patients in PFN group have fair results as well as 1 patient in DHS and no patient in PFN group has poor results.

Table 3: Intraoperative complications in DHS group

Complications	No of patients	Percentage
Improper insertion of compression screw	3	5.55
Varus angulation	4	7.84

According to table 3, the intraoperative complications like improper insertion of compression screw was found in 5.55% patients and varus angulation was found in 7.84% patients in DHS group. Three infection cases were identified in the DHS group;

these cases were managed with local debridement and antibiotics and implant removal was not necessary. One, which was discovered later, needed to have its implant removed and was treated cautiously.

Table 4: Intraoperative complications in PFN group

Complications	No of patients	Percentage
Failure to achieve closed reduction	3	5.88
Fracture of lateral cortex	0	0
Failure to put de-rotation screw	3	5.88
Fracture displacement by nail insertion	2	3.92

As per table 4, the complications like failure to achieve closed reduction was found in 5.88% patients, failure to put de-rotation screw in 5.88% and fracture displacement by nail insertion was found in 3.92% patients in PFN group.

In both groups, there was a single instance of nonunion. By comparing the radiographic amounts of sliding observed in both groups between the one-year follow-up and the immediate postoperative X-ray. Comparing the P.F.N group to the dynamic hip screw, it was seen that there was less slippage. The average duration of surgery done using PFN method was 48 minutes and DHS was 70 minutes. The average blood loss in PFN group was 120ml and DHS group was 250ml. It has been found that blood loss in PFN group was less which shows statistically significant association $p < 0.005$. Average incision size for PFN was 3 cm while for DHS group was 5 cm ($p < .05$).

Discussion

When treating intertrochanteric (IT) hip fractures, two well-established surgical techniques are PFN and DHS. Even though the DHS has shown excellent results, complications frequently arise, particularly when treating an unstable intertrochanteric fracture. On the other hand, PFN serves as a buttress to stop the proximal fragment from translating laterally, which is one of its advantages. The intramedullary location of the nail

and lag screw interface makes the implant more resistant to the binding force.

As per the current study, the complications like superficial infections were identified in 1 patient of PFN and 3 patients of DHS group. The Nonunion complication was found in 1 patient of PFN and DHS group each and implant failure was found in 3 patients of PFN and 4 patients of DHS group. Moreover, deep infection was found in 1 patient of both the groups. Apart from these, intraoperative complications like improper insertion of compression screw was identified in 5.55% patients and varus angulation was found in 7.84% patients of DHS group. Moreover, the complications like failure to achieve closed reduction was found in 5.88% patients, failure to put de-rotation screw in 5.88% and fracture displacement by nail insertion was found in 3.92% patients in PFN group. There were no statistically significant differences between the study groups when comparing the intra-operative findings ($p = 0.324$ for intra-operative complications).

According to the study performed by López-Hualda et al. (2023) [13], Trochanteric Fixation Nail

Advanced (TFNA) showed superiority ($p < 0.001$). The most unstable fractures were more common in the TFNA group (AO 31 A3, $p < 0.005$). Patients with more unstable fractures ($p = 0.005$) and significant dementia ($p = 0.027$).

In the study of Ravikumar, George and Shetty (2023) [14], the average age of patient was 53.642 ± 12.923 years in the DHS group and 67.285 ± 11.424 years in the PFN group. In the PFN and DHS groups, the average blood loss was 115 ml and 192 ml, respectively. Patients treated with PFN had an average operating time of 73 minutes, while patients treated with DHS had an average operating time of 101 minutes. In our study, the average duration of surgery done using PFN method was 48 minutes and DHS was 70 minutes. The average blood loss in PFN group was 120ml and DHS group was 250ml. It has been found that blood loss in PFN group was less which shows statistically significant association $p < 0.005$.

Moreover, the current study identified that the complications like failure to achieve closed reduction was identified in 5.88% patients, failure to put derotation screw in 5.88%, and fracture displacement by nail insertion was identified in 3.92% patients in PFN group. As per the study of Samant et al. (2022) [15], by contrasting the radiographic quantities of sliding that were seen in both groups between the immediate postoperative X-ray and the one-year follow-up. Less slippage was observed when the PFN group and the dynamic hip screw were compared.

Conclusion

From the study it has been concluded that functional outcomes of PFN and DHS are comparable in stable fractures, however, PFN performs better in unstable fractures. As per the outcome of the current study, there were no statistically significant differences between the study groups when comparing the intra-operative findings. The average blood loss in PFN group was 120ml and DHS group was 250ml. It has been found that blood loss in PFN group was less which shows statistically significant association $p < 0.005$. Moreover, there were less poor outcomes of PFN surgery. Therefore, it has been considered that PFN method of surgery is more accurate and beneficial for the patients to have better and faster recovery.

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